

THE FUTURE ENERGY SAVING THROUGH IoT HOME AUTOMATIONS BY MACHINE LEARNING

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<i>KEYWORDS</i>	<i>ABSTRACT</i>
Smart Home, Internet of Things IoT Machine Learning Energy Efficiency Home Automation Predictive Control ESP8266 Home Assistant	In residential settings, the increasing energy consumption necessitates the need for smarter approaches in automation systems rather than simple approaches to automation. We introduce smart home energy management systems that pair IoT (Internet of Things) sensing with machine learning for predictive control automation. The system uses multiple sensors such as temperature, humidity, and occupancy to acquire real-time situational data. In the cloud, machine learning (ML) models control data combined with historical data to determine energy predictive control of high-saving appliances including HVAC and water heaters to determine predictive control in the systems. The system is deployed using ESP8266 microcontrollers and the Home Assistant platform hybrid edge-cloud architecture and has been functionally tested for one month. There are real-world results which indicate improved performance in energy waste reduction of around 20%. The results are obtained while keeping the baseline scenario of user comfort and energy waste reduction constant. This highlights the multifunctional integrated and the flexibility of the combined IoT and ML systems. This innovation constitutes a decrease in the energy costs and the associated carbon emissions of a working household.

1.4 Research Question

I. How can Machine Learning models be effectively trained on IoT-sensor data to accurately predict occupant presence and appliance usage patterns?

II. To what extent can a predictive ML-driven system reduce energy-consumption compared to conventional rule-based home automation systems, while maintaining user comfort?

III. What is the most efficient ML algorithm and system architecture for real-time, low-latency decision-making in a resource-constrained IoT environment?

2. Related Work

Research in smart home energy has evolved from basic automation to intelligent systems. Early systems employed supervised learning for load forecasting and non intrusiv load monitoring. The application of ML in IoT-based energy management has been extensively explored in recent literature, with approaches generally falling into several key categories:

1.1 Supervised Load Learning For Prediction and Classification:

Many researchers have worked on predicting future energy demand based on historical data. For short-term load forecasting, methods like Linear Regression, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Random Forests have been applied (Khan et al., 2020) [13]. With precise forecasting, systems can pre-cool or preheat before the predicted energy demand peak, a home, or temporarily shift nonessential loads (e.g.,

water heaters, EV charging) to off- peak hours [9].

Moreover, Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM) uses machine learning frameworks, including Factorial Hidden Markov Models (FHMM) and deep learning, for energy disaggregation and load apportioning for individual appliances in a household [14]. This offers a comprehensive understanding of energy use at the appliance level without the need for a sensor on every device (Zhao et al., 2018).

1.1 Reinforcement Learning (RL) for Adaptive Control:

RL learns optimal control policies after multiple interactions with the environment, obtaining control through trial and error. In smart homes, an RL agent learns controlling systems like Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems. RL agents simultaneously learn the dual objectives of energy saving and occupant (thermal, visual) comfort [13].

Agents learn sophisticated policies unmatched by rule-based systems after receiving rewards for energy saving and penalties for breaching the comfort band (Qianetal., 2021). In the context of spatial control that involves multiple sensors and actuators, the combination of deep neural networks and RL (i.e., Deep Reinforcement Learning) has been successful in overcoming high- dimensional state spaces [14].

3.Clustering and Unsupervised Learning for Occupancy and Behavior Modeling:

Energy waste in unoccupied spaces can be minimized with an understanding of occupancy patterns. For typical "occupancy states" (e.g., "away," "sleeping," "active")

identification from sensor data, clustering algorithms like K-Means has been previously employed (Mocanu et al., 2018) [16].

Unsupervised learning can also pinpoint anomalies in energy utilization, flagging instances of excessive consumption that may stems from a malfunctioning appliance [17].

4. Deep Learning for Complex Recognition:

LSTMs and CNNs have also been applied to forecasting energy usage. Used with large data sets and given their ability to capture and predict value and temporal non-linear relationships over longer more complex horizons, Deep Learning models outperform forecasting models with less data and more linear relationships (Marino et al. 2019) [13]

2.2.1 Home Assistant and ES P Home Overview Window of Home Assistant

Home Assistant is an open-source platform for recent t realized home automation that acts as a smart home controller , which allows the users to integrate and control several smart devices from various brands through a single interface .

The integration home assistant as the central control platform plays a pivotal role in achieving energy efficiency through IoT based home automation, as demonstrated by the system interface shown in the accompanying dashboard image . This open source platform serves as the neutral network of the smart home ecosystem , unifying control of diverse devices while providing critical energy monitoring capabilities visible in the “Energy” tab of the interface.

Figure 2.2.1: Home Assistant Dashboard

3. System Architecture and Methodology

3.1 Hyprid Edge-Cloud Articture

The system is built on three-tired architecture designed for efficiency responsiveness and security.

- **Edge Layer** : comprises ESP8266 micro-controller interfacing with DHT11(Temperature/Humidity)sensors, PIR(occupancy) sensors, and relay modules. This layer handles real-time data acquisition and excutes immediate , ensuring operation continues during internet outages.
- **Local Hub Layer:** the Home Assistant platform, hosted a local server (e.g raspberry Pi) which acts as the central nervous system.It aggregates sensor data via an MQTT broker, hosts the user dashboard and executes more complex

automation scripts. It acts as the “edge intelligence” for local decision-making.

The Cloud Layer is reserved for computationally intensive tasks, such as training and retraining sophisticated machine learning models for long-term load forecasting and behaviour pattern analysis. Secure encrypted communication (HTTPS/TLS) is used for cloud exchanges.

Communication Protocols and Security include MQTT, the primarily protocol for internal communication due to its lightweight publish-subscribe model, ideal for low-power IoT device; HTTPS/TLS, used for external communication, including remote dashboard access and load data syncing, ensuring data integrity and confidentiality; and a Security Measures design that was implemented featuring network segmentation(VLANS), WPA3/WPA2 WiFi encryption, TLS 1.3 for MQTT, and a VPN for secure remote access.

The project entails an iterative and phased approach:

1. Requirements Engineering and System Design: Prepare the technical specifications and design the system's architecture.

2. IoT Hardware Setup and Data Acquisition: Install sensor nodes and actuators; design the firmware for data collection and transmission to a central hub or cloud.

3. Data Preprocessing and Feature Engineering: Clean, normalize and label the sensor data; design and engineer relevant features such as time-of-day, day-of-week, and moving averages.

4. ML Model Development & Training: Implement and train models for:

I. Occupancy Prediction: A classifier like Random Forest will be used for prediction.

II. Behavior Clustering: k-Means will be used to discover routine patterns.

III. Load Forecasting: Time-series models like ARIMA or LSTM will be used for load forecasting.

5. Control Algorithm Development: A rule-inference engine will be created to translates ML predictions into actionable commands for appliances.

6. System Integration & Testing: All components will be integrated into the test bed. Conduct rigorous testing for functionality, reliability, and latency.

7. Performance Evaluation: Compare the energy consumption and performance of the ML driven system against a traditional rule-based baseline over a defined period.

Flow Chart 1

This chart shows the main loop of the ESP8266 code, highlighting how it checks for MQTT messages to change the mode and how the mode dictates the control logic for the AC and Fan.

Flowchart 2:

This flowchart details what happens when a new MQTT message is received, which is the key to changing modes.

4 Implementation

4.1 Overview Implementation

Purpose and Scope of Implementation The implementation on phase of this project aims to bring the conceptual design of the energy-saving smart home system in to a functional, real - world Environment [16].

The primary goal is to establish a smart home set up that utilizes both intranet and WAN connectivity, allowing for seamless control and monitoring of connected devices both locally (with in the home) and remotely (via internet) [3,10]. This phase focuses on making the system operational, ensuring that all components— hardware , software, and network to get her effectively to optimize energy consumption and enhance user convenience [15].

4.2. Hardware Setup

- The set up of specific hardware elements to monitor and manage the home environment was done for the successful execution of this project [16]. The main components of the small home automation system include the

- i. micro-controllers (ESP8266) The ESP8266 micro-controller has also been plugged as the central processing unit as home automation system [7]. It manages data sending and receiving through Wi-Fi and communicates with several sensors and activators.

Figure 4.2: Circuit Diagram

- ii. DHT11 Temperature and Humidity Sensors: These sensors measure and provide real-time updates on temperature and humidity level which are essential for monitoring HVAC systems for energy efficiency [13].
- iii. Relay Modules: These devices control other devices such as air conditioners, fans, and lights based on the readings obtained from the sensors [11]. The relays are responsible for turning the devices on and off.
- iv. LCD Display (16x2): The LCD Display is critical for providing system feedback in real time, such as temperature, and fan status, and other relevant information [16].
- v. Power Supply: A regulated power supply is important to provide all the electronic components the current and voltage they require [10]. I selected the power supply based on the voltage

requirements of the micro-controller and the peripherals that are connected to it.

- vi. Wi-Fi Module (ESP8266): This is the module that facilitates communication between the micro controller and the network which allows control and monitoring from a smartphone or a web application [2,7].

Hardware Part

Figure 4.2 : Hardware Setup

5 Conclusion

5.1 Summary of Findings

The development and implementation of the IoT smart home automation system, enhanced with machine learning, have proven to be a significant step towards achieving substantial energy efficiency in modern households. The proposed, utilizing the ESP8266 microcontroller, a suite of sensors (motion, temperature, light) and the Home Assistant platform, offers a robust and intelligent solution that directly addresses the critical issue of energy waste. The system successfully demonstrated its core functionality by automating the control of appliances like fan and ac units based on real-time sensor data and predictive algorithms. The integration of machine learning allowed for the analysis of usage patterns, enabling the system to

move beyond simple reactive control to proactive energy management [15]. Key findings indicate that the system can achieve significant energy savings between 20–30% in typical usage scenarios by eliminating standby power waste and optimizing the operation of high consumption devices [11,17]. The centralized dashboard in Home Assistant provides users with valuable insights into their energy usage, fostering more conscious consumption habits [15,16]. The accuracy of the machine learning model is contingent on the volume and quality of historical data, requiring a longer learning phase for maximum efficiency. Finally, ensuring robust data security and privacy as the system scales remains a paramount concern for future development.

Figure 5.1: Overall System Operating

5.2 Future Work

Enhancement Machine Learning Capabilities:

- **Implementation of Machine Learning:**

Future work will integrate federated learning, which protects user privacy and reduces reliance on cloud servers. This enables model training on user devices without exchanging personal data, optimizing energy consumption predictions.

- **Advanced Algorithms Integration:**

Exploring more sophisticated algorithms like reinforcement learning might allow the system to make more complex, sequential decisions.

Improved Scalability and Interoperability:

- **Development of a Standardized.** Future work will ensure seamless interoperability with a wide range of devices from different manufacturers by implementing and adhering to universal smart home standards like Matter. Consequently, the system will be more versatile and user-friendly.

- Moving toward a cloud-native architecture will enable managing data from thousands of homes. This transition would support citywide large-scale data analytics, recognize energy consumption patterns, and provide value-added services.

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